

ferent between japonica and indica waxy rice starches, whereas the pasting temperature, final at 95°C, cooled to 50°C, and consistency were not significant. The results showed the differ-

ences between breakdown and setback amylograph viscosities because indica has higher value of peak viscosity than japonica waxy rice starch. ■

Physicochemical properties of japonica and indica waxy rice. Korea, 1996.

Characteristic	Waxy rice		LSD ^c
	Japonica ^a	Indica ^b	
	<i>Milled waxy rice</i>		
Chemical property			
Amylose (%)	2.0	2.6	*
Alkali spreading value (1-7)			
1.7% KOH	6.3	6.5	ns
1.4% KOH	3.8	3.8	ns
Protein (%)	7.5	7.6	ns
Mg (ppm)	887	893	ns
K (ppm)	2,239	2,676	**
Mg/K	1.28	1.09	**
Texturogram			
Hardness (kg)	9.83	6.95	*
Adhesiveness	-1.18	-1.20	ns
Cohesiveness	0.17	0.19	ns
Springiness	0.96	0.93	ns
Gumminess	1.47	1.24	ns
Chewiness	1.40	1.19	ns
	<i>Waxy rice starch</i>		
Water-binding capacity (%)	196	183	**
Gel consistency (mm)	78(S) ^d	88(S)	ns
Transmittance (% at 625 nm)			
<70 °C	23.9-32.4	28.9-42.7	**
≤70 °C	76.3-78.4	78.2-78.8	ns
Swelling power			
<70 °C	1.4-7.7	1.33-5.1	*
≤70 °C	over 20	over 20	ns
Amylography (RVU)			
Pasting temperature (°C)	70.2	70.6	ns
Peak	273	281	*
Final at 95 °C	99	98	ns
Cooled 50 °C	135	132	ns
Breakdown	173	183	*
Setback	-138	-149	**
Consistency	35	34	ns

^aJaponica = Sinseonchalbyeo, Buklukbanna, Wonsanchalbyeo, Iri309, and Hwaseonchalbyeo. ^bIndica = Hankangchalbyeo, Iri352, IR29, IR65, and RD6. ^c*,** = significant at 0.05 and 0.01 level, respectively. ns = not significant. ^dBased on Cagampang et al (1973) = S:soft (61-100 mm).

A method of producing Basmati rice aroma from *Bassia* flowers

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The aroma of Basmati rice was identified as 2-acetyl-1-pyrroline (AP) by Buttery and colleagues, and Schieberle developed a simple method of its synthesis from proline and sugar. Our

group slightly modified this method. We reported (IRRN 17(5):9,1992) that the sweet smell of some indigenous varieties of unboiled fragrant rice was the same as that of our synthetic product, and this product, although proline-based, was different from AP. Using gas chromatograph-mass spectrometer (GCMS) analysis, we tested pure AP from Schieberle's laboratory and have now established that the

fragrance of unboiled rice is the same as that of AP. We have also traced AP in the fresh flowers of *Bassia latifolia* in relatively large amounts. Because synthesis (by both Schieberle and us) is based on the Maillard reaction, it yields only microgram quantities of AP from grams of proline and sugar. For larger quantities, production of AP from *Bassia* was considered.

Paper chromatographic studies first established the *Bassia* fragrance as that of AP. We further confirmed this result using high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC; C18 microbondapak column, isocratic runs with methanol: water at 50:50, pump pressure 0.5 ml min⁻¹). Since we have found that AP-citrate remains stable for at least 6 mo, fresh flowers were macerated in excess citric acid, chromatographically purified, and compared with GCMS-tested standard AP, which was likewise treated with excess citric acid. Peaks for citric acid and AP-citrate were clearly visible in the standard and *Bassia* extracts. This observation may be the first one documenting the occurrence of AP in a flower. Steam distillation of *Bassia* flower and collection in pure citric acid thus yields AP-citrate that might be utilized after purification. ■

Effect of degree of polish on physical and gravimetric properties of rough rice

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Knowledge of rice's physical and gravimetric properties, such as grain size, bulk density, and porosity are important for designing systems for handling, transport, storage, drying, and other processes. Degree of polish is a most important parameter for trade purposes because milled rice quality, amount of bran, and oil content depend on it. This study determined the pro-

properties of three rice varieties (Pant Dhan 4, Pant Dhan 10, and Pant Dhan 121, collected from a university rice breeder, at 13 ± 1.00% dry basis grown in northern India. Cleaned rough rice was shelled, and unshelled ones were separated; brown rice was milled in a laboratory rice whitener (model Tm-25 Satake) for 10-110 s at 10-s intervals to attain different degrees of bran removal.

Relations between degree of polish, time of milling, milling yield, physical dimensions, and gravimetric properties were calculated by regression analysis. Only those models for which the *r* value was greater than 0.80 for linear relation were considered. The statistical results are summarized in the table. ■

Regression coefficient (*r*) and standard error of estimate (SEE) for grain characteristics with rate of bran removal. Pantnagar, India.

Grain characteristic	Pant Dhan 10		Pant Dhan 10		Pant Dhan 12	
	<i>r</i>	SEE	<i>r</i>	SEE	<i>r</i>	SEE
<i>Physical properties</i>						
Length (L)	0.700	0.200	0.690	0.060	0.650	0.057
Width (W)	0.985	0.007	0.883	0.030	0.860	0.015
Thickness (T)	0.886	0.035	0.925	0.023	0.860	0.015
Length-width ratio	0.630	0.107	0.054	0.046	0.109	0.032
Width-thickness ratio	0.693	0.020	0.550	0.027	0.969	0.009
L X W X T	0.959	0.695	0.960	0.533	0.936	0.370
<i>Gravimetric properties</i>						
Mass (M)	0.927	0.051	0.847	0.120	0.827	0.089
Bulk volume (VB)	0.915	0.177	0.942	0.111	0.841	0.279
True volume (VT)	0.810	0.149	0.841	0.141	0.936	0.049
Bulk density (DB)	0.959	0.229	0.960	0.136	0.936	0.365
True density (DT)	0.786	0.023	0.652	0.009	0.800	0.020

Effects of genotype x soil interaction on rice grain quality in japonica rice

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We evaluated quality (chemical components, texture of cooked rice, and amylogram characters) of rice grown under different conditions (soil texture, drainage, slope angle, and effective soil depth) (Table 1), using Dongjinbyeo,

the most widely cultivated variety in Korea.

The contents of Mg and Mg/K were lowest in rice grown in the Yaesan soil series, the most inferior soil. The hardness and chewiness, among textures of

cooked rice, were highest in rice grown in this same soil series. The values of maximum viscosity and breakdown were higher in rice grown in 4th class soil than those in 1st and 2nd class soils (Table 2).

Table 1. A classified standard soil class according to physical parameters for paddy field based on Korean soil series.

Soil series	Soil texture	Drainage	Slope angle (%)	Effective soil depth (cm)	Total soil class
Chonbuk	Clay-loam	Very rapid	<2	>100	1
Yongji	Clay	Rapid	2-7	50-100	2
Seongsan	Siltyclay loam	Moderate	7-15	20-50	3
Yaesan	Silt loam	Slow	>15	<20	4

Table 2. Effect of soil and environment on chemical components, texture, and amylogram characteristics of rice quality in Dongjin rice variety. Korea. 1995-96.

Soil series and location	Samples/location (no.)	Chemical component ^a							Texture of cooked rice ^a				Amylogram characters ^a			
		Amylose content (%)	Protein (%)	Fat (%)	Ash (%)	Mg (ppm)	K (ppm)	Mg/K	Hardness	Adhesive-ness	Cohesive-ness	Chewi-ness	Maximum viscosity	Minimum viscosity	Final viscosity	Break-down
Chonbuk at Iksan	9	18.4a	7.39a	1.40a	1.40a	832a	2074c	1.31a	5.78b	1.69a	0.36a	1.88b	402b	321a	571a	-169bc
Yongji at Changseong	6	17.7a	7.38a	1.40a	1.40a	840a	2173ab	1.25ab	5.17b	1.03a	0.32a	1.36b	442ab	318a	582a	-140b
Seongsan at Naju	6	17.6a	7.77a	1.43a	1.43a	837a	2137bc	1.15bc	4.85b	1.42a	0.34a	1.29b	429ab	325a	575a	-122b
Yaesan at Jeungup	6	18.0a	7.33a	1.40a	1.43a	761b	2226a	1.01c	9.14a	1.34a	0.36a	2.37a	484a	337a	564a	- 80a

^aMeans followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.